

Thracian Sparatakos=“Famed for (his) Success/Victories”; Thracian Amatakos=“Of Renowned Strength”; and analysis of some additional Thracian names ending in -tokos, -takos, -dokos

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Abstract

Besides the meanings that I posit for Sparatakos and Amatakos, in this paper I argue that in most Thracian names---and probably in all Thracian names---the element tokos/takos/dokos/dakus found at the end of a number of ancient Thracian anthroponyms meant “famous, renowned”, as was first posited a number of decades ago by other linguists, including Vladimir Georgiev and Ivan Duridanov (Georgiev may have been the first to posit that, but I leave that up to historians of linguistics to determine).

Perhaps in some names, the element tokos/takos/dokos/dakus may have meant “fitted for/suited to” and/or “accepting” or “holding”: but these latter three options cannot be the meanings of the element in all the attested Thracian names of this type.

Part 1: Spartacus

After considering numerous scenarios; after considerable reflection and meditation, I have come to the conclusion that the Thracian name Sparatakos/Sparatokos/Sparadokos (etc.)---widely known through the Latin form Spartacus---and attested from Crimea to Thrace---meant “Famous/famed for (his) successes, victories”, with Spara deriving from PIE **speh₁*- “to succeed, to prosper”, and cognate with the sperus portion of Latin

prosperus=“prosperous, successful; favorable; propitious”; the prosperus is from Proto-Italic *prosparos; additional cognates include Proto-Slavic **sporъ* “abundant, lavish”, from which derive a number of Slavic words as well as the Romanian word spor (“increase, progress, success”); a Romanian verb “a spori” meaning „to advance; make progress, make headway; to accumulate, multiply, increase”; and spornic, a Romanian adjective meaning „rich; plentiful, abundant; productive; useful, advantageous” (etc.). Sanskrit *sphira*, “fat, abundant” is another cognate.

The meaning “Famous spear” posited by Georgiev and accepted by Ivan Duridanov never felt proper nor right to me, because it is not the spear that was responsible for his victories nor for the victories of the other Thracians who bore the name before Spartacus and after him; the focus should be on the person wielding the spear, and with little doubt, the focus was indeed on the person wielding the spear. Besides, the meaning “spear” for words of that type are attested only in Germanic (cf. English “spear” and its Germanic cognates) and Latin (cf. Latin *sparus*, “hunting spear” etc.); while the PIE **speh*₁- “to succeed, to prosper” has offspring in many Indo-European languages.

There is attested once among Ancient Greeks an anthroponym Toxokleitos, which most likely means “Famous arrow/bow”: but in the end, I’m sure that does not impact the Thracian names I discuss in this paper.

Part 2---Amatokos/Amadokos/Medokos/Metokos (etc.)

There is a Thracian anthroponym, ethnonym, oronym and hydronym Ἀμάδοκος (Amadokos), also Amatokos (etc.), and the names Μήτοκος/Μήδοκος, Mētokos/Mēdokos (in Latin, known as Medocus) are usually considered to be variants of Ἀμάδοκος/Amatokos in a different Thracian dialect: that is what I believe as well.

The mountain and lake according to indications in Ptolemy’s Geography (the oronym is attested first in Ptolemy) was located in Ukraine (probably in Northeast Ukraine or North-central Ukraine), and was very likely named after the Thracian Amadoki people that Ptolemy records as being settled next to the

mountain, just as a lake near the mountain was also very likely named after the Amadoki.

The name itself---originally an anthroponym and/or an ethnonym according to my analysis---meant “Renowned/famous for (his) strength”, and in the ethnonym meant “Renowned/famous for (their) strength”, and a type of strength associated with military exploits, as we see in the Iranian languages where Ama was an Iranian deity who was a hypostasis of strength, and invoked in an Avestan hymn for success in military exploits/campaigns; in one verse, Ama is represented as hovering above Victory, and in a later verse (verse 45), the worshipper blesses Victory and Ama together¹.

The Sanskrit cognates are amisi and amanti, “to take hold of; to swear” both meanings deriving in my analysis from “strong, firm” leading to “to hold firmly>to hold” and “firm, strong>a binding oath>to swear”. The Ancient Greek cognate is ὄμνυμι (ómnumi)=”to swear (an oath)”. Michiel De Vaan posits that Latin amo (“to love”) derives from the root as well (see De Vaan’s etymological dictionary of Latin for his argument as to why).

The root is reconstructed as *h₃emh₃- by some, and as *h₂emh₃ in the LIV edited by Helmut Rix. You can check the literature for additional cognates, which I may enumerate in my next draft. I do not see a Baltic or Slavic cognate, which does not surprise me: Dacian and Thracian were much more like Phrygian and Greek and Albanian than like Baltic or Slavic, despite a number of close cognates with Balto-Slavic (but not as many as some argue).

Part 3: on the meaning of Takos, Tokos, Dokos in these Thracian names

The PIE root of Thracian Takos/Tokos/Dokos (Dokos may only occur due to Greek influence/adaptation) is *dek- which meant “to take; to fit”, and from there also shifting to “to perceive” in a number of IE languages, quite surely from “to take in” leading to “to perceive, understand”.

The semantic shift to “famous” is confirmed or nearly so in Ancient Greek, where we find δοκέω including the meanings “to expect” and “to be reputed” et al., as well as Ancient Greek δόξα: “expectation; opinion;

1 See the Encyclopaedia Iranica, the entry for Ama.

judgment; belief; repute” (the meaning “repute” deriving from the meaning “to expect”>”expected to be”>”reputed to be”; with “to expect/expected” deriving from “that which fits”) as well as some other meanings developing later.

It has been argued that an attested Bessi (a Thracian people) name Skuthodokos meant “Friendly/Hospitable to the Scythians”, with Dokos in this case meaning “accepting”, which does fit the older meanings of the PIE root of course, but the indications of Sparatokos and Amatokos and Metokos make me expect that in Skuthodokos the meaning again was “fame”: a famous Scythian? Or maybe the term Scythian derives from “to drive”, since PIE *(s)kewd- meant “to propel, to shoot” and thus could have referred to propelling the horse, not just to or primarily to propelling arrows ; so that here Skuthodokos means “Famous driver/Famous rider”, since the name Skuthodokos is attested on a ring which depicts only a man on horseback, no bow or arrows shown on the ring. Or maybe, despite no bows or arrows shown, the name Skuthodokos meant “Famous Archer”.

Part 4: Satokos/Sadokos; Sitalkes, Sitalkas, Sitalkos, and more

There was also a Thracian name Satokos/Sadokos, a Thracian man who was admired by the Athenians for helping them out. In the first draft of this work, I posited tentatively that Sa- of Satokos/Sadokos derives from PIE *swā- “healthy; whole; active; vigorous”, with cognates such as Latin sanus and Ancient Greek σῶς / σόος “safe and sound, alive and well”, the name perhaps again meaning “Renowned for his strength” or instead “Renowned for his integrity”. But it does not seem so likely to me that the Thracian cognate of Ancient Greek σῶς / σόος and Latin sanus would be simply “Sa”, and I have a better theory now.

As of December 30th 2023 I think it is very likely---to a probably high certainty---that the Sa of Satokos/Sadokos actually meant “very”, cognate with Ancient Greek Ζα (ζᾶ) which meant “very”, as in the Ancient Greek word ζᾶπυρος which meant “very fiery”. Thus Satokos/Sadokos would mean “Very Famous” which sounds like a likely name, a name that can simply be translated as “Renowned” or “Celebrated”. I first thought of this in the summer of 2023 or earlier, but I had forgotten about it, though I had noted it down on paper. It is

known from numerous examples that Thracian had a [Z<>S] vacillation, as seen with Svelsourdos/Zbelsoirdos, Salmoxis/Zalmoxis, Aulosanis/Aulozanis etc.

I also think that the Thracian name Σιτάλκης /Σίταλκος /Σιτάλκας represents a dialectical variant of Zi (“God”) which became Si, the form Zi being encountered in Thracian names such as Zipuros, which by consensus surely meant “Child of God”, with Thracian Zi cognate with Latin Deus and Greek Zeus, and Thracian puros meaning “child”.

I posit that Thracian τάλκης /ταλκος/τάλκας implied “child of, offspring of”, literally meaning “pushed out from/a sprout”, from PIE *telk, “to push; propel; throw out; strike, beat, pound” etc. That we are dealing with Σιτάλκης /Σίταλκος /Σιτάλκας and not with Σιτ-άλκης , Σίτ-αλκος, Σιτ-άλκας is very strongly indicated by the Thracian names Ροιμητάλκης (Rhoimētáلكēs), Ρυμητάλκης (Rhumētáلكēs), Rhoimēzenis (which is Rhoimē+zenis, with zenis being cognate with Ancient Greek -genés, “born of”, as seen in many other Thracian names ending with Zenus/Zenis/Zanis etc.). So compare Rhoimēzenis to Rhoimētáلكēs; then we see why the parsings Σιτάλκης /Σίταλκος /Σιτάλκας are so much more likely than Σιτ-άλκης , Σίτ-αλκος, Σιτ-άλκας : therefore, in the Thracian names Σιτάλκης , Σίταλκος, Σιτάλκας , we are more likely not dealing with the Ancient Greek word ἀλκή=“prowess, force; defense, guard; battle, fight”, but instead with a name that very likely meant “Sprouted from God”, with Si a dialectical variant of Zi=“God” in Thracian, as seen in Zipuros et al.

To return to Thracian Sa, which I think corresponds to Ancient Greek Za (ζᾱ) which meant “very”, I think that we also encounter this Sa in the Ancient Greek word σατύρος (“satyr; a lewd person”), which is to be compared with Ancient Greek τίτυρος (“satyr; bellwether ram; reed or pipe”), which is most likely a reduplication of “τύρ” (“swollen, virile”) from PIE *tewh₂- “to swell, to be strong”. Compare Ancient Greek τυρός (“cheese”) by consensus derived from PIE *tewh₂- “to swell, to be strong”, because of how cheese forms from the curdling/swelling of milk. The reduplication “ti-” at the beginning of tituros probably also functioned as an intensifier.

So a meaning of “swollen, virile” explains the meanings seen for τίτυρος : satyr ; a bellwether ram which leads the flock of sheep, thus the powerful, virile ram which leads the flock; and “reed, pipe” from their

resemblance to a penis: so a shift from “penis” to “reed, pipe” is probably what happened.

And what about σαῦρος (“satyr; a lewd person”)? I think it meant “Very Swollen, Very Virile, Very Horny” etc., referring to those preeminent and salient qualities of the satyrs. Sa=“Very”.

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